

Organic Compounds of Niobium : Reactions of Niobium Pentaethoxide with Nitrogen containing Reagents

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Reactions of niobium pentaethoxide with mono-, di- and tri-ethanolamines have been studied in presence of benzene and the following compounds have been isolated; $\text{Nb}(\text{OEt})_4(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2)$, $\text{Nb}(\text{OEt})_3(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH})$, $\text{Nb}(\text{OEt})(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH})_2$, $\text{Nb}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH})_2(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2)$, $\text{Nb}(\text{OEt})_2(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2)_2\text{N}$, $\text{Nb}(\text{OEt})_2(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2)_2\text{N}$ and $\text{Nb}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2)_3\text{N}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2)_2\text{NCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$. In all these reactions, the replacement of the hydrogen of the hydroxy group is quite facile, whereas further reaction is very slow and requires several hours of refluxing. The reaction of niobium pentaethoxide and excess ethylenediamine yielded finally $\text{Nb}(\text{OEt})_3(\text{HNCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH})$. Molecular weights of benzene-soluble compounds have been determined ebullioscopically in benzene.

A considerable amount of work has been done on organic derivatives of niobium and the technique of alcohol interchange in presence of benzene has been used in the preparation of alkoxides¹, β -diketonate² and β -ketoester³ derivatives of niobium. No work appears to have been done on the derivatives of niobium alkoxides with organic ligands containing nitrogen. Some anhydrous complexes of amines with niobium pentachloride has been described by Fowles and coworkers^{4,5}. Recently, the reactions of alkoxides of boron⁶, aluminium⁷, titanium⁸, tin⁹ and germanium¹⁰ with ethanolamines have been studied and interesting results have been obtained. In view of the above, it was considered of interest to study the reactions of niobium pentaethoxide with mono-, di- and tri-ethanolamines.

Reaction of niobium pentaethoxide with one mole of monoethanolamine was found to liberate two moles of ethanol in the azeotrope and the resulting product on analysis was found to correspond in composition to niobium triethoxide monoethanolamine derivative. This reaction can be represented as :

1. Mehrotra and Kapoor, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1966, 10, 354.
2. Kapoor and Mehrotra, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1965, 8, 346.
3. Mehrotra and Kapoor, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1964, 7, 176.
4. Fowles and Pleass, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 2078.
5. Carnell and Fowles, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1962, 4, 40.
6. Mehrotra and Srivastva, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 521.
7. Mehrotra and Mehrotra, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 677.
8. Puri and Mehrotra, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 447.
9. V. D. Gupta, *Ph.D. Thesis* (1965); Rajasthan University, Jaipur.
10. Mehrotra and Chandra, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 497.

However, when the above reaction was carried out in equimolar ratio at room temperature, the product was found to have composition of niobium tetra-ethoxide mono-ethanolamine derivative :

Reactions were further carried out in 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 molar ratios and were found to proceed with liberation of four and five moles of ethanol respectively :

In all these reactions, the replacement of the hydrogen of the hydroxy group is quite easy whereas further reaction is very slow and requires several hours of refluxing. The formation of niobium-nitrogen bonds in these derivatives is of special interest because niobium pentaethoxide differs markedly from those of boron⁶, aluminium⁷ and titanium⁸ in which cases the amino group of the ethanolamine appears to be ineffective in the replacement reactions and only the hydroxylic hydrogen appears to be active. However, with germanium⁹ and tin¹⁰ alkoxides observations similar to those being reported for niobium pentaethoxide were made. Some evidence that basic nitrogen is able to coordinate with niobium is provided by existence of a water insoluble complex with 8-hydroxyquinoline¹¹ and solvolysis reactions of niobium pentachloride with ammonia¹², primary and secondary amines¹³. Fairbrother and Taylor¹³ have reported that freshly precipitated niobic acid readily dissolves in aqueous solutions of ethanolamines with the formation of five membered chelate rings. Recently, the presence of niobium-nitrogen bond in the complex $\text{Nb}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_7\text{H}_2$ has been confirmed by infra-red study¹⁴.

Reaction between diethanolamine and niobium pentaethoxide in 1 : 1 molar ratio proceeded with the liberation of three moles of ethanol in the azeotrope:

11. Kasner, Garcia-Porrata and Grove, *Analyt. Chem.*, 1955, **27**, 492.

12. Fowles and Pollard, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4938.

13. Fairbrother and Taylor, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 4946.

14. Ghuskova, Ershova and Polikarpova, *Lzv. Akad. Nauk SSSR. Neorg. Materialy*, 1965, **1**, (4), 488.

The reaction of niobium pentaethoxide with diethanolamine in 1 : 2 molar ratio did not proceed to completion and only 4.5 moles of alcohol could be distilled out even under careful fractionation. It was further observed that niobium diethoxide diethanolamine derivative was allowed to react with one mole of diethanolamine, only 1.5 moles of ethanol was detected in the azeotrope. The non-formation of the pure bis-derivative appears to be due to steric factors.

With one and two moles of triethanolamine, the pentaethoxide of niobium liberate three and five moles of ethanol respectively:

All these reactions were carried out in the presence of benzene and ethanol produced was fractionated azeotropically. The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating the alcohol by an oxidative method¹⁵. The products were isolated by removing the excess benzene by distillation or filtration and finally drying under reduced pressure.

The derivatives (i) and (iv) are brown solids, soluble in benzene. They decompose with charring when heated under reduced pressure. The products (ii), (iii) and (vi) are yellow brown solids, almost insoluble in benzene and these decompose on heating under reduced pressure. The product (v) is found to volatilise under reduced pressure and found to be highly soluble in benzene.

The molecular weights of the soluble ethanolamine derivatives of niobium were determined in boiling benzene. The results obtained are given below :

Compound	Molecular Weight		Molecular Complexity
	Found	Calc.	
*Nb(OEt) ₅ (monoethanolamine)	734	287	2.55
*Nb(OEt) ₅ (diethanolamine)	786	285	2.75
Nb(OEt) ₅ (triethanolamine)	954	329	1.08

Recently Mehrotra and Gupta⁹ have shown the reactivity of amino groups in ethylene diamine to be similar to that of ethanolamines towards stannic isopropoxide. These workers have isolated a disubstituted product when reaction in equimolar or excess ethylene diamine was carried out with stannic isopropoxide. In view of the above, the reaction of niobium pentaethoxide with ethylene diamine (excess) was studied and only two

15. Bradley, Halim and Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3450.

*The accuracy of these determination is rather low as these derivatives tend to undergo depolymerisation on refluxing in benzene.

moles of ethanol could be distilled out:

After removing the volatile fractions the insoluble yellow powder was obtained which decompose on heating under reduced pressure. The reaction with ethylenediamine was found to be comparatively much slower than with ethanolamines. The hydroxy groups of the ethanolamines react quite readily and in the chelated products of the type

$\begin{array}{c} \text{H}_2\text{C}-\text{O} \\ | \\ \text{H}_2\text{C}-\text{N} \\ | \\ \text{H}_2 \end{array} \text{Nb}(\text{OEt})_4$ formed initially the reaction appears to be more facile than the initial reaction of ethylenediamine.

EXPERIMENTAL

All-glass apparatus was used with precautions to exclude moisture. Molecular weights were determined ebullioscopically in benzene.

Benzene was dried as described¹⁵. Niobium pentaethoxide was prepared by ammonia method¹⁶. Mono-, di- and tri-ethanolamines were distilled before use. Ethylenediamine was dried over aluminium isopropoxide and finally fractionated.

Niobium was estimated as niobium pentoxide¹⁷. Ethanol in the azeotrope was estimated by back titration method¹⁸. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl method.

1. Reaction between niobium pentaethoxide and monoethanolamine (Molar Ratio 1 : 1):

To niobium pentaethoxide (2.29 g) dissolved in benzene (40 g) was added monoethanolamine (0.44 g). The amine settled down in the solution as a separate layer. On shaking slowly, a light turbid solution was obtained which became clear after few minutes. The reaction mixture was refluxed and azeotrope was collected between 68-80° in about thirty hours. On cooling a brown solution was obtained. After removing the excess solvent under reduced pressure, a brown pasty solid (1.99 g), soluble in benzene, was obtained. Found: Ethanol in the azeotrope; 0.63 g (two moles require, 0.66 g). Found: Nb, 33.3; N, 4.7%; Mol. wt., 734. Calc. for $\text{Nb}(\text{OEt})_5(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4\text{NH})$: Nb, 32.4; N, 4.9%. Mol. wt., 287.

The above compound decomposes when heated under reduced pressure.

2. Reaction between niobium pentaethoxide and monoethanolamine (1 : 1) at room temperature :

A white turbid solution was obtained when monoethanolamine (0.52 g) was added to a benzene (4 g) solution of niobium pentaethoxide (2.68 g), which became clear after few minutes. The contents were left overnight and volatile fractions were removed under reduced pressure. A yellow brown viscous liquid (2.80 g), decomposed at reflux, was obtained. Found: Nb, 27.7; N, 4.0%. Calc. for $\text{Nb}(\text{OEt})_4(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)$: Nb, 27.9; N, 4.2%.

16. Bradley, Chakravarti and Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2381.

3. *Reaction between niobium diethoxide diethanolamine and diethanolamine (Molar ratio 1:1):*

Diethanolamine (0.38 g) was introduced into a benzene (40 g) solution of the compound (1.03 g). The reaction mixture was refluxed under a fractionating column with careful fractionation of the ethanol produced in the reaction azeotropically with benzene. After removing the excess solvent under reduced pressure, a yellow brown solid (1.13 g), insoluble in benzene, was obtained. Found: Ethanol in the azeotrope 0.23 g (1.5 moles require 0.25 g). Found: Nb, 29.1; N, 8.3%. Calc. for Nb (OEt)_{0.5} (O₂C₄H₉N)₂: Nb, 28.9; N, 8.7%.

4. *Reaction between niobium pentaethoxide and ethylenediamine (Molar ratio 1: excess):*

Niobium pentaethoxide (1.98 g), ethylenediamine (2.63 g) and benzene (40 g) were mixed together. The colourless reaction mixture was refluxed under a column with slow fractionation of the ethanol produced in the reaction. After removing the excess of the solvent at the room temperature (15-20°) under reduced pressure, a benzene insoluble fine yellow powder (1.75 g), was obtained. Found: Ethanol in the azeotrope 0.62 g (two moles require 0.58 g). Found: Nb, 32.6; N, 9.8%. Calc. for Nb(OEt)₅ (N₂C₂H₆): Nb, 32.5; N, 9.8%.

TABLE I
Reactions of niobium pentaethoxide with ethanolamines

Nb- (OEt) ₅ in g.	ethano- amine in g.	Molar Ratio	Amount of alcohol in azeotrope		Product, yield and state	Action of heat	Analysis			
			Found In g.	Calc. in g.			Found		Calc.	
							Nb %	N %	Nb %	N %
Monoethanolamine										
2.29	0.44	1:1	0.63	0.66	Nb(OEt) ₅ (monoethanol- amine (1.99 g), brown pasty solid.	Decomposes on heating.	33.3	4.7	32.4	4.9
2.37	0.92	1:2	1.33	1.37	Nb(OEt) ₅ (monoethanol- amine) ₄ (1.94 g), brown yellow solid.	-	36.4	10.7	36.3	10.9
1.88	1.08	1:3	1.26	1.36	Nb(monoethanolamine) ₃ - (1.54 g), yellow brown solid.	-	33.4	13.6	34.9	15.5
Diethanolamine										
1.92	0.64	1:1	0.81	0.83	Nb (OEt) ₅ (diethanolamine) (1.78 g), brown pasty solid.	-	32.6	4.9	32.6	4.9
1.46	0.97	1:2	0.95	0.95	Nb(OEt) _{0.5} (diethanol- amine) ₂ (1.46 g), yellow powder.	-	28.9	8.7	28.9	8.7
Triethanolamine										
2.65	1.24	1:1	1.14	1.15	Nb(OEt) ₅ (triethanol- amine) (2.77 g), yellow viscous liquid	173°/0.2 mm	28.3	4.0	28.2	4.3
1.82	1.71	1:2	1.34	1.32	Nb (triethanolamine) ₂ (2.27 g), white solid		24.0	7.2	24.1	7.3

Since the general procedure is the same the reactions of niobium pentaoxide with mono-, di- and tri-ethanolamines are given in table I.

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